

ASPIRIN-INDUCED UPPER GASTROINTESTINAL BLEEDING: A CASE REPORT

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ABSTRACT

Aspirin is widely used for the prevention of vascular events but is associated with a sustained increase in the risk of significant bleeding. Aspirin is used in coronary artery disease (CAD) for secondary prevention to reduce the risk of heart attacks and strokes by inhibiting platelet aggregation. However, it carries risks such as gastrointestinal bleeding, stomach ulcers, and allergic reactions, especially in individuals with pre-existing conditions. This case report discuss of a woman with CAD with no prior history of gastrointestinal disease, presented with hematemesis after prolonged use of aspirin.

KEYWORDS: Aspirin, Upper Gastrointestinal Bleeding, Hematemesis, Proton Pump Inhibitors.

INTRODUCTION

Aspirin is more frequently used in the prevention and treatment of cardiovascular diseases, there are many evidences show it have the high potential to cause gastrointestinal (GI) bleeding, especially in the older population.^[1] The ASPREE (The Aspirin in Reducing Events in the Elderly) trial, focusing on individuals aged 70 and above,

reported the incidence was 2.1 events per 1,000 person-years in the aspirin group, compared to 1.1 events per 1,000 person-years in the placebo group.^[2] This case report shows that aspirin-induced GI bleeding can occur even after prolonged, symptom-free use, underscoring the need for ongoing risk evaluation in elderly patients on antiplatelet therapy.

CASE REPORT

A 70-year-old female patient presented with complaints of hematemesis (5 episodes for past 1 day), chest pain, headache, and generalized weakness. The patient had a known history of hypertension, triple vessel coronary artery disease for 2 years, with medication history of T. Nifedipine 20mg TDS, T. Enalapril 2.5mg BD, T. Aspirin 150mg OD, T. Clopidogrel 75mg OD, T. Atorvastatin 20mg OD, T. Metoprolol 25mg BD, T. Ranitidine 150mg BD. On observation, the patient weight was normal (BMI = 22.2 kg/m²), blood pressure at the time of admission was 170/110 mmHg, pulse rate was 85/min and temperature were 98.6F. She was pallor and dehydrated.

Blood culture shows no bacterial growth. In ECHO, the Left Ventricular Ejection Fraction was found to be 40% that indicated Heart Failure with moderate Ejection Fraction. Hemotologic examination shows Prothrombin Time: 14.4 Sec, and INR: 1.06. Her hemoglobin level was 9.9 g/dL, serum sodium was 130 mmol/L, serum potassium was 3.5 mmol/L and serum chloride was 103 mmol/L.

This condition was managed by 1 unit of Packed Red Blood Cells (PRBC), 4 units of Fresh Frozen Plasma (FFP), 1000ml of Normal Saline (NS), 1000ml of Ringer's Lactate (RL), and 500ml of Dextrose Normal Saline (DNS) at a rate of 80 mL/hr, Ceftriaxone 1g IV BD, Metronidazole 500 mg IV TID, tranexamic acid 1g in 100ml NS, Pantoprazole in two different dosages: an initial STAT dose of 80 mg IV, followed by 8 mg/hr IV, Ondansetron 8 mg IV, Labetalol 20 mg IV was administered as a STAT.

On our investigation we found that her admission complaint of hematemesis was occurred due to dual anti platelet therapy and there were more chances for aspirin in facilitating the reaction. The Adverse drug reaction was identified and confirmed using Naranjo scale which has the score of 8 and the severity was assessed by using Hartwig severity assessment scale, which shows the severity falls under the category of Level 5. Aspirin was discontinued from her regular treatment plan. The dual antiplatelet therapy was changed to monotherapy (Clopidogrel 75 mg orally) and her regular medication was started such as Metoprolol 25 mg orally BD,

Enalapril 2.5 mg orally BD, Spironolactone 25 mg orally OD, Atorvastatin 40 mg orally. Her hematemesis was stopped and condition improved.

Patient was discharged with omeprazole 20mg, clopidogrel 75mg, atorvastatin 40mg, metoprolol 25mg, spironolactone 25mg, enalapril 2.5mg. The patient was advised to follow up with their primary care physician and to follow a specific diet.

DISCUSSION

In this case report the patient experienced Aspirin induced upper GI bleed. Mahady SE et al conducted a randomized controlled trial (RCT) in older people who are using aspirin found the incidence of GI bleeding was increased by 60%.^[2] Our case also supporting the evidence of this RCT as the older women due to prolonged use of Aspirin experiences GI bleed. The ADR was found and reported to PvPI. And the effective measures were taken to rectify the ADR as the dual anti-platelet therapy was converted into monotherapy. According to the ACC/AHA guidelines, Clopidogrel was given as Monotherapy for minimizing the risk of bleeding. Injection Pantoprazole was given according to the standard treatment workflow in acute gastrointestinal bleeding as per ICMR guidelines.^[4,5]

Aspirin-induced upper GI bleeding is a notable concern, especially in older populations who use multi antiplatelet or antihypertensive medications with cardiovascular comorbidities. This case stresses the need for meticulous patient selection, dose optimization, and gastroprotective measures, such as concomitant use of proton pump inhibitors (PPIs). Clinicians should balance more on the benefits of aspirin therapy against its considerable harms in high-risk populations and monitor gastrointestinal symptoms regularly to prevent adverse reactions.

CONCLUSION

This case report highlights the risk for upper gastrointestinal bleeding as a complication of aspirin use, particularly in patients with underlying risk factors such as advanced age and concurrent use of other medications. It also emphasizes the importance of careful assessment before initiating aspirin therapy, especially for prophylactic purposes. Patient education, regular monitoring, and the use of gastroprotective agents like proton pump inhibitors can help reduce the risk of GI complications.

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